

School-Based Feeding Program: Parents' Views on Their Children's Nutrition and Education

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Abstract. This qualitative narrative study explored parents' perceptions and experiences regarding their children's participation in school-based feeding programs. Through in-depth interviews and thematic analysis, the research aimed to uncover parents' perspectives on the impact of these initiatives on family dynamics, child nutrition, and educational engagement. The study involved ten parents with children studying at five different elementary schools in the Schools Division of IGACOS. They were chosen based on the following criteria: parents of elementary students who were wasted and severely wasted; their children were beneficiaries of the School-Based Feeding Program; and their children were currently in grades 1-6. Findings revealed that the school-based feeding program positively influenced children's nutrition, improving their nutritional status and physical, social, and emotional well-being. Parents also viewed the program's impact on their children's education as beneficial, noting improvements in academic performance, school attendance, and participation. Insights from parental perceptions highlight the importance of good nutrition and the need for proper resource allocation and program implementation. Given the paramount importance of children's nutrition, educational leaders and stakeholders must collaborate to ensure these children have healthier lives.

KEY WORDS

1. school-based feeding program 2. nutrition 3. children

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1. Introduction

School-based feeding programs, which aim to address malnutrition among young children and solve the problem of educational underachievement, have become a significant intervention not just in our country but worldwide. However, despite the substantial resources dedicated to these programs, parents' perspectives, who are essential stakeholders in their children's health and education, are frequently disregarded. It is essential to comprehend parents' perspectives on SBFs because they offer valuable information about the program's acceptability, efficacy, and possible areas for development. The nutritional status of a student has a substantial impact on their learning ability and academic success. When a student's diet lacks necessary nutrients or suffers from malnutrition and hunger, their ability to learn declines compared to their well-nourished, healthy classmates. Inadequate nourishment impedes cognitive growth and the ability to successfully engage in the learning process. When compared to their well-nourished peers, severely malnourished students are at a higher risk of

grade repetition and dropping out of school. Irregular school attendance among extremely undernourished children is a serious issue that affects their academic performance. Even brief hunger, which is prevalent among children who go to school hungry, can hurt their learning, resulting in difficulties with concentration and doing complicated activities (Garcia Meer, 2021). Wang and Fawzi's (2020) systematic review and meta-analysis study offers a broad perspective on the effects of school feeding programs. The study suggested that these programs can significantly improve the nutritional status of the children, either by weight or height, and encourage them to attend school regularly, thereby boosting school enrollment and attendance. A school-based feeding program is an effort that provides meals or snacks within the school setting. It is recognized as a valuable investment in education and a method to improve children's access to education worldwide. Millions of children in developed nations such as the United States, Japan, and the United Kingdom have benefited from long-standing School-Based Feeding Programs (SBFPs). As evidenced by physical growth and cognitive aptitude assessments, these programs primarily target disadvantaged children. Their key goals are to improve students' school attendance, enrollment, academic achievement, and nutritional well-being (Agujar, Villanueva, Santos, 2020). The Department of Education, specifically the Bureau of Learners Support Services-School Health Division (BLSS-SHD), is responsible for carrying out the SBFP under DepEd Order No. 39, issued in 2017 and known as the operational guidelines for the School-Based Feeding Program (SBFP) for the school years 2017-2022, and DepEd Order No. 018, issued in 2019 and known as the Supplemental Guidelines for the implementation of SBFP for the fiscal year 2019. This program is intended to fight malnutrition among public school children. SBFP comprises all Severely Wasted (SW) and Wasted (W) students in kindergarten through

sixth grade. The program's primary goal is to improve the nutritional status of the recipients and to attain at least a 70Lu and Dacal's (2020) study offers a closer look at a specific school feeding program in the Philippines. The results show positive effects on the physical growth and academic performance of the children who participated in the study. This study provides valuable insights into the potential benefits of school-based feeding programs, but its specific focus limits its generalizability. Another study by Yamaguchi and Takagi (2018) in the Philippines examined the school-based feeding program that targets the undernourished children in the country. The study focuses on the implementation and impact of the program, offering practical insights. This study provides valuable information for developing targeted interventions to create better policies and guidelines to improve the program. In the locality of Island Garden City of Samal, specifically in Babak District, it has been observed that many children are suffering from malnutrition due to poverty and unhealthy food habits. For this reason, the local government, through the schools around this area, implements the school-based feeding program to alleviate child hunger and improve the children's health and nutrition. School administrators and staff, particularly the teachers, play a significant role in this program's success. Their role in the success of this implementation is crucial to supporting the program in combating malnutrition among students. There are many studies about the school-based feeding program and its success in enhancing children's nutritional health. However, there are only a few studies conducted on parents' viewpoints on their children's nutrition and education. This research gap pushed the researcher to delve deeper into this topic. Children are widely recognized as a country's most valuable and essential resource, as they are the ones who will shape and build the future of the nation. Their health and well-being should be prioritized, especially

in primary education, because this is a vital stage of their development. This study explores parents' viewpoints regarding the school-based feeding program at five elementary schools in Babak District in Island Garden City of Samal.

The study's conclusions will add to the body of knowledge about the benefits of school-based feeding programs and offer valuable insights into educational management.

1.1. Purpose of the Study—The purpose of this study is to investigate and understand the viewpoints of parents about School-Based Feeding Programs and how they perceive the results of these programs. This study looked specifically at how parents evaluate these programs regarding their impact on their children's nutrition and education. This study aims to contribute to a thorough knowledge of the effectiveness of school-based feeding efforts in promoting better nutrition and improving academic achievements among schoolchildren by gathering insights into the attitudes and experiences of parents. The primary focus of the data collection was on the parents' views on the school-based feeding program and on their children's nutrition and education. The results of this phenomenological study will help us comprehend the advantages of the school-based feeding program and its impact on the nutrition and education of elementary school students. The insights collected from this study have the potential to influence educational management strategies, government policy, and regulations meant to enhance and improve the health and nutrition of every child in the country.

1.2. Research Questions—This study intends to explore parents' viewpoints about the School-Based Feeding Program and how they perceive the program's results. The research was executed to address the following inquiries:

- (1) What are the views of parents on the School-Based Feeding Program?
- (2) How do parents perceive the result of School-Based Feeding Programs on their children's nutrition and education?
- (3) What educational management insights can be drawn from the findings of the study?

1.3. Definition of Terms—For a more comprehensive understanding, the following terms were described operationally. School-Based Feeding Program (SBFP) was one intervention that addressed the undernutrition of school children in the Philippines by providing meals or

snacks (Mojica-Sevilla, 2023). Malnutrition was defined as a state of nutrition in which a deficiency or excess (or imbalance) of energy, protein, and other nutrients causes measurable adverse effects on tissue/body form (body, shape, size, composition), body function, and clinical outcome (Meier Stratton, 2004).

1.4. Significant of the Study—The researcher hopes that this study was beneficial to identified sectors of the academe. This includes the educational leaders, school heads, teachers, parents, other stakeholders, and future researchers. Educational leaders. Educational leaders could benefit from this study's findings because it could provide them with

insights regarding the results of School-Based Feeding Programs, which would allow them to implement programs aiming to support and improve the well-being of the students. The school heads. The findings of this study might help the school heads or principals be aware and informed about the need to enhance the employment of School-Based Feeding Programs

in their schools. The teachers. Teachers can benefit from this study by knowing their roles in improving their students' nutritional health through learning from the views of the parents on the perceived results of the School-Based Feeding Program to their children. The parents. Parents could benefit from this study by reflecting on the program's goals, applying them to

their households, and providing their children with healthy and balanced meals. Other stakeholders may provide better support to enhance the students' quality of life, particularly their nutrition and well-being. Future researchers. This would be helpful as an additional contribution to their references for future research in the field of School-Based Feeding Programs.

1.5. Theoretical Lens—The theoretical underpinning of this study is anchored to Abraham Maslow's most well-known theory, Maslow's Hierarchy of Needs, which was published in 1943. According to this idea, human motivation and behavior are driven by a hierarchy of needs, with the most basic wants at the bottom and higher-level demands emerging as lower-level needs are met. School-based feeding programs aim to provide nutritious meals to students, particularly those from low-income families, while at school. These programs address the lower levels of Maslow's Hierarchy of Needs by providing essential nutrition, ensuring a safe and secure environment, fostering social connections, and promoting self-esteem. By meeting these basic needs, these programs lay a solid foundation for students to focus on their education and personal growth. The study was further reinforced by Aaron Beck's cognitive behavioral theory way back in 1960. Cognitive Behavioral Theory (CBT) is a psychological paradigm that emphasizes the complex interplay of ideas, emotions, and behaviors, recognizing how they shape one another. When applied to investigating the perceived benefits of a school-based feeding program on students' nutrition

and overall well-being, the possibility of students developing negative cognitive habits appears. Students facing hunger or food poverty may develop negative thought patterns about their ability to concentrate and perform well academically. For instance, people may believe that their hunger affects their ability to focus or that their academic achievement is compromised. CBT can be an excellent tool for identifying and correcting these cognitive distortions, encouraging a more constructive mentality that contributes to kids' increased well-being and academic accomplishment. Cognitive behavioral theory might be applied to students who are beneficiaries of school-based feeding programs to address the cognitive distortions and emotional issues that may occur due to food poverty. By making regular meals available, these programs lay the groundwork for CBT interventions to assist kids in improving their cognitive patterns, emotions, behaviors, and, eventually, academic achievement. A friendly setting, nutritious meals, and CBT practices can all contribute to a happy and conducive learning environment for students. Figure 1 presents the conceptual framework of the study. It shows three interconnected working themes.

2. Methodology

This chapter effectively addressed the study's specific objectives by outlining the systematic procedures and methodologies used in phenomenological research. It also explained the selected research design and my roles as the researcher throughout the study's implementation. Moreover, it offered thorough insights into the research subjects, clarifying their procedures and selection

Fig. 1. The Conceptual Framework of the Study

standards. The chapter concludes by exploring the techniques used for data collection and analysis and the strategies used to uphold ethical standards during the research.

2.1. Philosophical Assumptions—A study’s philosophical and qualitative presumptions were vital in steering the investigation. Four fundamental assumptions—ontological, epistemological, axiological, and methodological—form the bedrock for comprehending qualitative research. These assumptions establish the groundwork for the research design and inform the researcher’s approach to the study. A classic example was the assumption that participants in a study would answer survey or interview questions honestly and factually. Since it would take considerable time and effort to validate answers of each participant, we assume honest responses. A paradigm was discussed as the broad framework or perspective that guides and shapes how researchers approach their studies, formulate research questions, gather data, analyze findings, and interpret results. It encompasses a set of beliefs, assumptions, methodologies, and theoretical foundations that influence how researchers conceptualize and conduct their research (Zukauskas et al., 2018).

In this research, the paradigm guided the choice of methodology, methods, and techniques, shaping the overall research process and ensuring coherence in the study. **Ontology.** This part of the research pertains to how the issue relates to the nature of reality. According to Creswell (2012), the reality was subjective and multiple, as seen by participants in the study. The ontological issue addresses the nature of reality for the qualitative researcher. The reality was constructed by individuals involved in the research situation. Thus, multiple realities exist, such as the realities of the researcher, those of individuals being investigated, and those of the reader or audiences interpreting the study. In this study, the focus was on the parents’ viewpoints on the School-Based Feeding Program on their children’s nutritional health, and how they perceive the program’s results on the education of the students was discussed by the participants. As well as educational insights gained from the findings. **Epistemology.** This refers to the awareness of how knowledge claims are justified by staying

as close to the participants as possible during the study to obtain firsthand information. Guba and Lincoln, as cited by Creswell (2012), state that the researcher attempted to lessen the distance between themselves from the participants on the epistemological assumption. He suggests that, as a researcher, he or she collaborates, spends time in the field with participants, and becomes an ‘insider’. Based on Davidson (2000) and Jones (2006), researchers identified phenomenology with the use of thematic analysis as the best means for this type of study. In this regard, individual researchers “hold explicit belief.” This study intended to gather information from the participants or the parents of elementary students who are considered malnourished and are beneficiaries of the School-Based Feeding Program in San Antonio Elementary School in Island Garden City of Samal, Babak District. It was assured that there was an establishment of close interaction with the participants to gain direct information that would shed light on the knowledge behind the inquiry, particularly on the viewpoints of the parents on School-Based Feeding Programs on children’s nutritional health and how they perceive the results of the program on the education of their students. Axiology. It concerns the influence and importance of my values as a researcher in this study. According to Creswell and Poth (2018), acknowledging and openly discussing the researcher’s values that shape the study is crucial. The values that influence how data are interpreted and presented were explicitly recognized in the research process. As a researcher, I handled each participant’s narrative with care and integrity and always

had the utmost respect for the information they provided. This commitment guaranteed that the participants’ answers were communicated truthfully, mirroring both their individual and research values. Methodology. According to Crotty (2020), this was defined as “the strategy, plan of action, process, or design lying behind the choice and use of particular methods and linking the choice and use of the methods to the desired outcomes.” Its objectives were to explain, assess, and defend procedures. This study focused on the parents’ viewpoints on the School-Based Feeding Program on their children’s nutritional health and how they perceive the program’s results on the education of the students was discussed by the participants using a qualitative methodology. To support the ontological and epistemological tenets, techniques like focus groups and interviews are employed, enabling a thorough and sympathetic examination of participants’ stories. These techniques were chosen because they can successfully convey the complexity and depth of the participants’ experiences. Rhetoric. In research, rhetoric was the skillful and convincing use of language, communication strategies, and presentation tactics to effectively communicate concepts, claims, and conclusions to sway the audience’s opinion and comprehension of the study (Beqiri, 2018). I utilized an engaging and respectful narrative style that honors the participants’ voices while effectively communicating the significance of the findings. This method not only made the research more accessible to read but also guaranteed that the interpretations were strong and based on the participants’ experiences.

2.2. *Qualitative Assumptions*—Using a phenomenological research methodology, my goal is to explore the parents’ viewpoints on the School-Based Feeding Program on their children’s nutritional health and how they perceive

the program’s results on the education of the students discussed by the participants. My objective was to gather information about their views, perceptions, and educational insights concerning the phenomenon I was studying. Utiliz-

ing phenomenology as my guiding qualitative framework, I uncovered the essence and significance of the roles played by these individuals, emphasizing their unique viewpoints and the intricate details of their experiences. As the study's qualitative researcher, I supported a level of investigation that goes beyond cursory observations. My research investigated the views, perceptions, and educational insights of the participants in relation to the phenomenon. I emphasized the significance of understanding the complexities of the human experience

2.3. Design and Procedure—Determining the precise approach used in a study is crucial in order to customize the best research design, data collection strategy, and data analysis approach to the study's objectives. I used a qualitative research design in this investigation. Hammersley (2013, cited in Aspers and Corte, 2019) states that studies characterized by verbal rather than statistical analysis are appropriate for qualitative research. Since I studied the views, perceptions, and educational insights of parents to the School-Based Feeding Program, the qualitative design was the most appropriate. This means that rather than establishing or refuting theories, I described and elaborated on this phenomenon. However, specialized methods were used in qualitative research, including grounded theory, narrative, case studies, phenomenology, and ethnography. Using a qualitative phenomenological research design, I explored the viewpoints of the participants in this

2.4. Research Participants—Qualitative analyses typically require a smaller sample size than quantitative analyses. Qualitative sample sizes should be large enough to obtain feedback for most or all perceptions. Obtaining most or all the perceptions leads to the attainment of saturation. Saturation occurs when adding more

in light of the various perspectives that were shaped by unique contexts, backgrounds, and personal histories (Neubauer et al., 2019). My study placed a strong emphasis on in-depth interviews, reflective dialogues, and the analysis of participants' narratives to capture the profound and complex school-based feeding program. I hope to contribute a thorough and contextually rich understanding of the views, perceptions, and educational insights related to the School-Based Feeding Program while upholding phenomenological principles.

particular setting. I selected this approach because, according to Asper's (2009, cited in Aspers and Corte, 2019) work, the scientific side of phenomenological research focuses on communicating the viewpoints of the subjects and the importance of their experiences, then applying scientific concepts to analyze these perspectives. Furthermore, Creswell (2018), stressed that a phenomenological study was a method of inquiry that describes the complex and collective experiences of the participants with respect to a particular phenomenon. A key idea in phenomenology was to reduce one's interpretations of a particular phenomenon to a description that could be applied to all situations. Therefore, I identified a phenomenon that revolves around the viewpoints of the participants in the School-Based Feeding Program. I then collected information from people who have direct experience with this phenomenon in order to create detailed and accurate descriptions.

participants to the study does not result in additional perspectives or information. Glaser and Strauss (2017) as cited in Hennink and Kaiser (2022) recommend the concept of saturation for achieving an appropriate sample size in qualitative studies. For phenomenological studies, Creswell (1998) recommends 5 to twenty-five

25, and Morse (1994) suggests at least 6. According to Subedi (2021), larger samples in qualitative studies hinder an in-depth exploration of the study phenomenon. There are no specific rules when determining the appropriate sample size in qualitative research. Qualitative sample size may best be determined by the time allotted, resources available, and study objectives (Patton, 2002 as cited in Mullet, 2018). The participants of this study consisted of 10 parents with children studying at five elementary schools in Babak District, Island Garden City of Samal. These schools are San Antonio Elementary School, Kinawitnon Elementary School, San Agustin Elementary School, Angel Villarica Central Elementary School, and Jose Cabunillas Elementary School. Two participants would represent each school; one for

the In-Depth Interview and one for the Focus Group Discussion. The participants were chosen based on the following criteria: they have to be the parents of elementary students who are wasted and severely wasted, their children are currently beneficiaries of the School-Based Feeding Program, and their children are currently in grades 1-6 and enrolled in any of the elementary schools mentioned above. I utilized the purposive sampling design, which is also known as judgmental, selective, or subjective sampling. The participants were chosen based on the criteria or purpose of the study (Creswell, 2018). The selection of the participants was purposefully done to ensure that the findings would be authentic (Marshall, 1996, as cited in Vasileiou et al., 2018).

2.5. Ethical Considerations—Ethical considerations were crucial because they relate to the moral principles and guidelines that govern my conduct as a researcher. These principles ensure that I carry out my investigations responsibly, treating participants with respect and striving to generate reliable and precise information. To protect participants, maintain scientific integrity, and foster trust within the research community, I adhered to established ethical standards in my research practices (Resnik, 2020). Social value. This concerns the potential benefits and favorable outcomes that research can bring to society, like addressing problems or improving people's quality of life. I evaluated the societal value of my study by acknowledging its potential impact and importance for the larger community. This ensured that resources are directed toward research that has the potential to create significant advantages for society. Informed Consent. This involved obtaining a participant's voluntary agreement to participate in a research study after they have been provided with sufficient information about the study's pur-

pose, methods, potential drawbacks, and benefits. In this research involving parents, it was my responsibility to ensure that the participants fully understood the study and their rights. This explanation allowed them to make an informed decision about participation, thereby preserving dignity and ensuring consent. Vulnerability. The vulnerability of research participants pertains to their increased risk of experiencing harm, exploitation, or coercion due to factors such as age, cognitive ability, or socioeconomic status. As a researcher, it was crucial for me to acknowledge and consider the potential vulnerability of these participants and take appropriate measures to protect them. This involved providing additional safeguards and support, such as obtaining informed consent ensuring confidentiality, and carefully explaining their rights and the study's procedures in a way they can understand. Additionally, I modified research methods to minimize potential adverse effects, ensuring that the well-being of these parents is prioritized throughout the study. Risks, benefits, and safety. In research, it was essential to

carefully evaluate the potential risks and benefits associated with participation in a study, as well as to implement measures that safeguard the well-being of participants. These elements involve assessing the potential disadvantages and advantages of participating in a study, along with establishing strategies to ensure the welfare of participants. In this investigation, as the researcher, I meticulously assessed and balanced these factors, ensuring that the potential benefits outweigh the risks. I put adequate precautions in place to minimize harm while optimizing the safety of participants, particularly considering the vulnerabilities of student participants. This comprehensive approach was crucial to maintaining ethical standards and protecting the participants throughout the research process. Privacy and confidentiality. Privacy and confidentiality in research are about safeguarding participants' personal information and ensuring their identity remains confidential unless they explicitly consent to disclosure. In the context of this study, I was responsible for implementing appropriate protocols to secure participants' data and maintain confidentiality. This includes anonymizing data, securely storing information, and limiting access to authorized personnel only. These measures were crucial to protect the privacy of student participants and uphold the integrity of the research process. Justice. This concept relates to the equitable allocation of the advantages and disadvantages resulting from research across various segments of society. In this study, I ensured that my research was inclusive, avoiding the exploitation or exclusion of vulnerable groups. Additionally, I strived to make the research's benefits accessible to all who could benefit from them. This approach promotes fairness and equity throughout the research process, ensuring that no group bears an undue burden or is left out of the potential gains from the findings. Transparency. Transparency in research encompasses maintaining integrity at every phase of the study, from its concep-

tion and execution to the reporting of results. In this study, I offered clear and truthful information regarding my research methodologies and outcomes. Furthermore, I was receptive to examination and feedback. Transparency acts as a catalyst for trust, credibility, and accountability, not only within the research community but also among the general public. This commitment to openness ensured that the process and results of my research were accessible and understandable to all stakeholders involved. The qualification of a researcher. The qualification of a researcher relates to one's academic background, professional experience, and proficiency in a particular area of study, ensuring that one possesses the requisite abilities and knowledge to conduct the research competently. In this investigation, I held suitable qualifications that showcase my capability to conduct research, analyze data, and interpret the results. My expertise and training provided the foundation necessary to approach this study with a rigorous scientific method and critical analytical skills, ensuring the integrity and validity of the findings. The adequacy of facilities. This addresses the presence and suitability of the essential resources, tools, and infrastructure required to execute a study efficiently and securely. In this research, I guaranteed access to appropriate facilities for conducting the investigation. This access facilitates the creation of credible and consistent findings and mitigates potential risks to study participants. Having the right facilities ensures that the data collection and analysis processes are conducted under conditions that uphold the highest standards of research integrity and safety. Community involvement. This encompasses the dynamic involvement and active engagement of community members, stakeholders, or the intended study population throughout the research journey, from initial planning to sharing research outcomes. In this study, I engaged the community to guarantee the study's relevance, acceptability, and potential impact.

Additionally, this involvement fosters trust and cooperation between me and the community. Engaging with the community not only helped to tailor the research to be more effective and meaningful but also enhanced the overall quality and applicability of the results. Plagiarism and fabrication. Researchers should strictly follow principles of academic honesty and integrity. This entails giving proper credit to the work of others, presenting original contributions, and

2.6. Role of the Researcher—As an unbiased research facilitator and promoter, I was responsible for ensuring that the research process was conducted fairly, objectively, and without personal bias, prejudice, or influence from outside sources. I created an environment that encourages the open and honest exploration of ideas and promotes fairness in data collection and analysis. This commitment to impartiality helps to uphold the integrity of the research process and ensures that the findings are reliable, and representative of the true phenomena being studied. As an expert in qualitative methods, I was familiar with various qualitative research techniques, such as interviews, focus groups, and participant observation. I possess the skills and knowledge necessary to design, conduct, and analyze qualitative studies, ensuring that the research question was satisfactorily addressed and that the results were legitimate and dependable. My expertise in these methods allowed me to deeply explore complex social phenomena and capture the nuanced experiences of participants, contributing to the validity and reliability of the research findings. As a data collector and keeper, my responsibility was to gather information from various sources such as interviews or observations, and to ensure accurate and secure storage of this information. I followed ethical guidelines, safeguarded participants' privacy, and ensured that data was structured and avail-

verifying the accuracy and authenticity of data. In this study, I employed tools like plagiarism detectors and maintained thorough documentation of my research procedures to ensure that my work was devoid of plagiarism and that all data and discoveries were authentic and reliable. By upholding these principles, I enhanced the credibility and trustworthiness of the research community.

able for later examination and understanding. This careful management of data was instrumental in maintaining the integrity of the research process and supported the production of credible, reliable findings that can be reviewed and utilized by others in the academic community. As a data analyst, I analyzed the gathered data to discover trends, patterns, and valuable perspectives in accordance with the research query. I utilized meticulous qualitative data analysis methods like coding and thematic analysis to extract significant findings and enrich the knowledge base within my discipline. This approach allowed me to deeply understand the data, providing insights that were not only relevant but also contribute significantly to the field, enhancing scholarly discussions and practical applications related to the study topic. Finally, as an organizer and presenter of data, I was tasked with synthesizing and communicating the research findings concisely and coherently. This entails skillfully conveying the study's objectives, approaches, outcomes, and ramifications through written documents, presentations, or alternative means of transmitting information. I ensured that the research results were easily accessible and comprehensible to the designated audience. This approach helps to maximize the impact of the findings, ensuring they were not only shared but also understood and utilized by others in ways that could further knowledge and influence practice in the field.

2.7. *Data Collection*—This study employed a systematic data collection procedure. Several steps were taken to adhere to the proper data collection procedure, which ensured the accuracy and objectivity of the data collection. The following was the step-by-step process of gathering the data needed. Securing endorsement from the Dean of Graduate School, the Schools Division Superintendent, and the School Principal. To initiate the data collection process, I secured endorsements from key stakeholders including the Dean of the Graduate School at Rizal Memorial Colleges, the Schools Division Superintendent, the School Principal, and the parents of the participants. This process involved submitting formal letters outlining the research objectives and methodology, accompanied by any supporting documents. This crucial step took place within the first week of November 2023, ensuring that all necessary permissions were in place before proceeding with the collection of data. This proactive approach not only facilitated compliance with ethical standards but also fostered a cooperative environment among all parties involved. Asking permission from the Schools Division Superintendent. Upon receiving the endorsement, I requested permission from the school's division superintendent. This required submitting a formal letter detailing the research proposal and its significance to the educational community. Along with the letter, I attached Chapters 1 and 2 of my dissertation and the research instrument, clearly explaining the study's objectives and the process of participant identification. Moreover, I waited for the response from the Schools Di-

2.8. *Data Analysis*—Upon the completion of data collection, I embarked on the systematic process of data coding and thematic content analysis. This involved the careful structuring of transcribed data into categories, subcate-

gories, and themes derived from the interview dialogues. By discerning patterns and connections within the data, I was able to formulate conclusions and glean insights directly related to the research objectives. This rigorous process vision Superintendent (SDS) before proceeding with the data collection. This step was undertaken during the second week of the month of November 2023, ensuring that all necessary approvals were in place to conduct the research ethically and effectively. Asking for permission from the school heads. Once permission was granted, I sought approval from the school heads of the selected institutions. This step involved submitting formal request letters to each school head, outlining the research's purpose and the expected data collection timeframe. I asked for permission to conduct the study from the third week of November 2023 to the last week of the same month. Obtaining consent from the participants. With the school heads' approval, I asked permission from the participants during the last week of November 2023. They were formally oriented about the study and the process they would go through as participants. Conducting the interview. Upon securing consent from all participants, I conducted an in-depth interview using the interview questionnaire in the same week. I took the participants' profiles, jotted down notes, and the participants wrote their answers on the questionnaire provided. I carefully examined and scrutinized the answers to identify recurring themes. After the interview sessions, I undertook the meticulous task of transcribing the interviewees' responses. This involved a careful consideration of non-verbal cues and contextually relevant details, ensuring that the breadth of participants' reactions was accurately captured. The transcription process, which utilized audio recordings and field notes, was completed during the first week of December.

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ensured that the data was interpreted effectively, accurately reflecting the experiences and perspectives of the participants. In this study, I employ Creswell's Thematic Analysis approach, which was particularly suited for encompassing a range of perspectives and portrayals in participants' feedback. Adopting thematic analysis authenticates the portrayal of individual components and facilitates the categorization of identified patterns within the provided responses. Thematic analysis, a qualitative research technique, is used to recognize, scrutinize, and interpret patterns or themes present within qualitative data in textual, visual, or other formats. As a qualitative research approach, thematic analysis allows researchers to systematically arrange and dissect complex data sets, providing a reassuring structure to the research process. It involved searching for overarching themes that encapsulate the narratives embedded within the data. This process necessitates the identification of themes through meticulous examination and repeated review of transcribed data (Dawadi, 2020). This methodical approach helps ensure that the analysis is both comprehensive and reflective of the data collected, providing

2.9. *Framework of Analysis*—The analytical framework in phenomenological research was a methodical and structured approach to data analysis, interpretation, and presentation. When selecting an analytical framework, there was no single solution that was suitable for all problems. The choice depends on the nature and complexity of the issue, the purpose and goal of the analysis, the availability and quality of data, time and resource constraints, and the audience and stakeholders involved. In this research study, I used Colaizzi's method to analyze data from the interviews and discussions of the participants' viewpoints on the School-Based Feeding Program. According to Morrow et al. (2021), Colaizzi's (1978) method

features a distinctive seven-step process that offers a rigorous analysis, closely adhering to the data at each stage. This method culminates in a concise yet comprehensive description of the phenomenon under study, which was validated by the participants who experienced it. The effectiveness of this approach relies on rich first-person accounts of experiences, which could be collected through various means. Although face-to-face interviews are common, data can also be gathered from written narratives, blogs, research diaries, online interviews, and other forms. This method enables researchers to uncover emergent themes and explore the intricate relationships between them (Wirihana et al., 2018). Data Familiarization. By reading deep insights into the study's objectives. Therefore, I used Creswell's Thematic Analysis in my research, which necessitated extensive theming and transcript interpretation. According to Caulfield (2020), there are multiple essential phases in Creswell's Thematic Analysis, including familiarization, coding, generating themes, reviewing themes, defining and labeling themes, and writing up. I became fully immersed in the intricacies and subtleties of the content as I became acquainted with the data to begin this process. After that, I started categorizing the data using semantic richness to group different informational components. I created themes that encapsulate the main ideas of the data using these codes. After that, these themes were examined and improved upon to make sure they appropriately depict the dataset. Every theme has a definition and name that elucidates the fundamental ideas. The last step entailed combining the themes and insights into a cohesive article that clearly conveyed the study's conclusions. This methodical approach guaranteed a comprehensive examination and enhanced the comprehension of the information.

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and rereading the transcripts several times, I fully understood the meanings conveyed by the participants and gained a global sense of the phenomenon being studied. This thorough review process was crucial for fully grasping the nuances of participants' statements, enabling a deeper analysis of their experiences. Identifying Significant Statements. I carefully identified every statement in the narratives that was directly related to the phenomenon I was studying. To identify and highlight phrases and descriptions that shed light on the particular experiences under study, a thorough examination of the gathered data, such as written narratives or transcripts of interviews, must be conducted. This step was essential to ensuring that my analysis stayed on topic and provided a strong basis for future thematic development. Formulating Meanings. After carefully examining the important statements, I determined meanings that are pertinent to the phenomenon. Although Colaizzi admits that complete bracketing was never truly possible, I had to reflexively "bracket" my own presuppositions to stick closely to the phenomenon as experienced. To guarantee that the analysis stays rooted in the participants' real experiences, this process entails putting aside my own interpretations as much as was practical. Clustering Themes. By grouping the identified meanings into themes shared by all accounts, I ensured a rigorous analysis that remained true to the participants' experiences. Throughout this process, presuppositions must be bracketed, especially to avoid any possible influence from existing theories. Letting the themes naturally

arise from the data rather than being influenced by outside forces preserved the integrity of the analysis. Developing an exhaustive description. I incorporated every theme generated in the previous step into a comprehensive and all-encompassing description of the phenomenon that I wrote. By identifying common themes from the participant accounts, this thorough description conveyed the essence and complexity of the phenomenon. By taking this step, it was ensured that the final representation presents a comprehensive perspective of the experiences that each participant has had. Producing the fundamental structure. I broke down the lengthy explanation into a succinct statement that highlights the key elements that I believe were crucial to understanding the phenomenon's structure. This succinct synthesis effectively and concisely communicates the essence of the participants' experiences, concentrating on the essential components necessary for comprehending the phenomenon. Seeking verification of the fundamental structure, I asked participants if the fundamental structure statement accurately reflects their experience by returning it to all participants. I then went back and changed the earlier stages of the analysis in light of their comments. Through this iterative process, the validity and credibility of the findings increased, and the analysis remained firmly based on the participants' perspectives. The following figure illustrates this rigorous process, highlighting each step to comprehensively explain the actions taken to comprehensively analyze the data.

2.10. Trustworthiness of the Study—The trustworthiness of a study was about how reliable, sensible, and authentic the research results were, ensuring that the conclusions were trustworthy and accurate. In qualitative research, factors like credibility, transferability, confirmability, and dependability are often used to evalu-

ate how reliable the study was. These considerations are further described below, according to Guba (1981). Credibility. Building credibility entails proving that the results were accurate. Credibility was important for this study because it evaluates whether the results accurately represent the realities and viewpoints of parents

Fig. 2. Analytical Framework of the Study

regarding the School-Based Feeding Program. I conversed with the participants for a long time in order to gain a thorough understanding of their experiences and to increase my credibility. I also used triangulation, gathering information from a variety of sources, including observations, interviews, and maybe questionnaires. In order to confirm the interpretations, I gave the parents a preliminary version of the findings as part of member checking. Transferability. The degree to which this study's results can be used in different situations or with different populations is referred to as transferability. While the particular insights were closely linked to parents' viewpoints in a specific educational environment, I gave thorough explanations of the research context and methodology. The study's transferability was increased because this thorough, rich narrative enables others, including educators, school administrators, and researchers, to assess how well the results apply to comparable contexts or populations. Confirmability. Confirmability deals with the study's objectivity by making sure that the respondents, not my personal prejudices or biases, shaped the findings. I kept a thorough audit trail that details every step

of the research process, from data collection to data analysis decisions, in order to ensure confirmability. This methodological transparency made it possible for other researchers to evaluate the research's objectivity by following the study's development and going over the choices made. Dependability. Dependability means proving that the study results are reliable and repeatable in similar situations. This study's dependability was attained through meticulous documentation of the entire research procedure, including the methods used for data collection and analysis. By ensuring that other researchers can duplicate the study and possibly produce consistent results, such documentation validates the research's dependability. By following these standards, the research not only offered valid and trustworthy conclusions regarding the viewpoints of the School-Based Feeding Program to the parents, but it also offered a framework that researchers and other educators could use to compare similar learning environments. This methodology enhanced the study's standing in the academic community and provided insightful information for upcoming studies and instructional design.

3. Results and Discussion

This chapter presents the results generated from the analysis of the gathered data from the interview, including the themes and a comprehensive discussion that answers the objectives of the study. The themes that emerged from the gathered data were discussed in this chapter. The result presents the description and background of the participants along with their assigned pseudonyms to hide their identities.

3.1. Views of Parents on School-Based Feeding Program—School-based feeding programs play an important role in addressing food insecurity among students by providing a source of nutrition critical to their growth and academic success. However, parents' views toward these programs are diverse and complex, influenced by factors ranging from socioeconomic status to cultural beliefs. According to Fowler (2012,

as cited in Jacob and Musa, 2021), considering the perspectives of stakeholders such as parents is crucial when designing programs to effectively address the needs and expectations of the targeted population. Children from low-income households frequently experience undernourishment and physical weakness due to insufficient access to nutritious meals essential for their health and well-being. Limited finan-

cial resources often compel parents to prioritize inexpensive foods that lack adequate nutritional value. Consequently, this compromises the child's development. In this part of the study, the views of the parents regarding the school feeding program will be explored with a focus

3.1.1. Improved Nutritional Status—The school-based feeding program is a huge help in improving children's nutritional status, especially among economically disadvantaged groups. By providing balanced, fortified meals during the school day, these programs address nutritional deficiencies and promote healthier eating habits among children. Many low-income children's access to nutritious food is limited, resulting in nutritional deficiencies that can have a negative impact on their growth, development, and health. By providing nutritious meals at school, the feeding program directly addresses these deficiencies, ensuring that children get the vitamins, minerals, proteins, and carbohydrates they need for growth and well-being. These meals are frequently carefully planned to meet nutritional guidelines and standards, providing a well-balanced source of nutrients that children may not have at home. I interviewed ten parents whose children are beneficiaries of the school-based feeding program. During the interview, they were asked about their thoughts regarding the school-based feeding program in improving their child's nutrition and well-being. The participants have mentioned that because of the program, their children are healthier because of the nutritious

3.1.2. Enhanced Physical Health—By providing regular and nutritious meals during the school day, the school-based feeding program significantly improves children's physical health. These programs combat malnutrition, promote healthy growth, and lower the

on its impact on their children's nutrition and well-being. Through interviews with participants, three recurring themes emerged, each of which will be comprehensively examined and analyzed individually.

food provided to them. According to one participant (PS2), their child used to be underweight and sickly but since the program, they are doing much better than before. This finding is supported by Flores (2023) who stated that both parents and students perceived that the school-based feeding program improved their health. Additionally, the results of the study conducted by Dada et al. (2023) indicated that the meals provided by the government satisfied the student's nutritional needs in terms of the amount, quality, and regularity. Belonging to a low-income family, the usual foods provided at home are noodles and canned goods. Children rarely get to eat meat and fruits because of how expensive it is, and their parents cannot afford them. According to one participant (PS5), the program greatly improved the nutrition of their child. This corroborates the study of Solania and Cubillas (2020) who emphasized that the school feeding program has improved the dietary diversity and nutritional status of the children. Moreover, the aforementioned assertion is corroborated by Zenebe et al. (2018), whose study, rooted in both qualitative and quantitative research, revealed a beneficial impact of the School Feeding Program (SFP) on the nutritional status and school attendance of children within the district.

incidence of conditions such as stunted growth and nutrient deficiencies. They reduce illness-related absenteeism by supporting immune function with key nutrients. Furthermore, by educating children on nutrition and healthy eating habits, these programs encourage them to

make better food choices, resulting in long-term health benefits. The provision of healthy and nutritious meals by schools through this program ensures that children receive sufficient nutrients to maintain their health. Consuming nutrient-rich foods such as vegetables, fruits, meats, and others enables them to gain the energy needed to engage in physical activity at school. During the interview, participants were questioned about their perspectives on the school-based feeding program's role in enhancing their child's nutrition and well-being. Proper nutrition is vital to avoid impeding the child's physical growth, particularly considering their natural inclination toward activity and playfulness. It is crucial to provide meals that supply them with sufficient energy to support their active lifestyle. According to one participant (PS1), before benefiting from the meals offered by the program, her daughter used to feel weak and tired but now she is more energetic and active. This result

3.1.3. Social and Emotional Well-being — The financial status of a family significantly affects the nutritional status of a child belonging to that family. Fortunately, there are programs that offer food assistance to help parents provide proper meals to their children. This, in turn, reduces stress associated with food insecurity and instilling a sense of community in students. This program provides a nurturing environment in which children can thrive socially, emotionally, and academically. To delve deeper into the topic, the participants were asked about their thoughts regarding the influence of school-based feeding programs on their child's nutrition and well-being. An improvement in their child's emotional and social well-being has been reported by the participants since they started benefitting from the meals provided by the feeding program in schools. According to one participant (PS4), her child used to feel embarrassed during mealtime because her meal was not as delicious as the others but since the program,

aligns well with Barroga et al. (2016 as cited in Candelanza and Comighud's (2020) study highlighting that sufficient nutrition is crucial for the appropriate growth and development of children. The mental and physical development of children in their early years necessitates access to nutritious and wholesome foods. Furthermore, adequate and balanced nutrition plays a crucial role in ensuring the expected growth and development of children according to their age, while also boosting their resistance to diseases. According to one participant (PS3), she noticed a significant improvement in her child's health, transitioning from appearing pale and weak to displaying a brighter and livelier demeanor. According to Mukhamedzhanov et al. (2023), the significance of healthy eating habits acquired in childhood extends to bone development, enhanced cognitive abilities, improved school performance, and the prevention of certain diseases later in life.

her child found friends she could eat with during school lunch. Being recipients of this program can sometimes lead to the perception that they belong to a lower socioeconomic class, which can create a negative impression among the beneficiaries leading to food insecurity and discrimination. This aligns with the idea of Semegn et al. (2023) who pointed out that previous to the program's launch, only students from low-income homes were qualified to participate—a measure that a number of participants emphasized as encouraging discrimination. They further added that the participants of their study talked about how the school feeding program promoted more harmony and social cohesiveness among kids, which decreased incidences of prejudice. This was especially true when students enjoyed meals together, regardless of the socioeconomic situation of their families. The participants of this study have also mentioned that their children found friends they could eat with during mealtime at school. According to

Fig. 3. Views Of Parents on School-based Feeding Program

the pieces of literature presented in this study, the meals provided by the school-based feeding program have helped improve the physical health of the children by giving them proper and nutritious meals needed to give them energy throughout the day. However, the program not only provides children with balanced and nutritious meals but also promotes the social and emotional well-being of the students. According to one of the participants (PR8), she has seen how the program boosts their child's confidence and happiness because the school has created a supportive space where they feel accepted and valued. This finding is similar to a study conducted by Cervato-Mancuso et al. (2013 as cited in Eluya, 2019) who stated that school meals not only function as a source of nutrition but also a means of promoting social connection between students and those who help prepare their meals. The authors further added that these lunchtime get-togethers are also seen

as important chances to support kids' social and emotional growth. Another participant (PR6) also mentioned that the program not only gives the children meals but also helps them feel part of the school community by boosting their confidence and helping them make friends which in turn makes them happier. According to Candelanza and Comighud's (2020) study, students who participated in classroom activities after the feeding program reported increased physical activity, improved mental acuity when completing academic work, and increased sociability when interacting with others. Having to eat delicious meals with friends puts students in a good mood and also affects how they act around others. Figure 3 shows parents' views on a school-based feeding program and the emergence of the themes of social and emotional being, improved nutritional status, and enhanced physical health.

3.2. Parents' Perception of the Results of School-Based Feeding Programs on their Children's Education—

Parents' perceptions of the impact of school-based feeding programs on their children's education can differ depending on a variety of factors such as socioeconomic status, cultural beliefs, and personal experiences. Many parents see these programs as invaluable resources that improve their children's educational outcomes. These programs ensure that children are well-nourished and can concentrate in class, resulting in improved academic performance. Parents may also value the indirect benefits of these programs, such as lower absenteeism due to illness and increased motivation to attend school on a regular basis. Furthermore, some parents may see school-based feeding programs

as a source of financial relief, allowing them to redirect resources toward other educational expenses such as school supplies or extracurricular activities. This can lead to feelings of gratitude for the program and belief in its positive impact on their children's educational journey. The previous part of the paper discusses the influence of school-based feeding programs on children's nutrition and well-being, in this part of the study, the discussion will be focused on how the parents perceive the impact of school-based feeding programs on their children's education. The interview with the participants revealed two themes which will each be discussed comprehensively.

3.2.1. Better Academic Performance—Parents frequently see school-based feeding programs as critical to their children's academic success. These programs provide nutritious meals during the school day, ensuring that children have the energy and focus required to learn effectively. Additionally, they relieve financial burdens on families, allowing them to invest in other educational needs. Improved nutrition enhances cognitive function, allowing children to retain information and solve problems more effectively. These programs reduce hunger and food insecurity while also encouraging regular attendance, which is critical for academic success. When discussing the advantages of the school-based feeding program, participants were questioned about their perception of how the initiative impacted their children's academic performance. The participants believed that the reason why their children are doing better in school is because of the meals provided by the school-based feeding program. By receiving proper and balanced meals, children no longer have to worry about being hungry and can focus more on their academics. According to one participant (PS3), she believes that the reason why her child is so eager to

learn is because the healthy and nutritious meals provided by the program give her child more energy to learn. Having one less problem to worry about, the children can focus their attention on the discussion. This finding corroborates the assertion made by Candelanza and Comighud (2020) that proper diet and sufficient sustenance have the potential to improve children's academic achievement as well as their general success in the classroom. Additionally, this also aligns with the study of Semegn et al. (2023) which highlighted their participants' responses that school feeding program reduces hunger and health difficulties while having a favorable impact on student's academic performance and school enrollment. The study outcomes emphasized the favorable influence of school food programs on students' academic performance and dropout rates. According to Kassu (2023), school feeding has been identified as crucial in improving children's learning capacity and attention span, particularly by easing short-term hunger in the classroom. Based on their observations and conversations with their children, the participants were able to validate their assertions that the school-based feeding program helps improve their child's aca-

demic performance. According to one participant (PS2), their child's participation in the class has increased and their grades are improving. Another participant (PR6) also noted that the meals provided by the program ensure their children feel full, resulting in increased alertness and engagement in class, ultimately leading to improved grades. This result is supported by Filgona et al. (2020) who found that the reason for the students' improved academic performance could be that they paid close attention in class after receiving satisfactory food through the government-sponsored school feed-

3.2.2. Increased School Attendance and Participation—Parents also perceive school-based feeding programs as successful in boosting their children's attendance and participation in school. These programs provide a consistent source of nutritious meals during the school day, potentially alleviating hunger and food insecurity, which are common barriers to regular school attendance. When children know they will be fed at school, they are more likely to attend regularly, lowering absenteeism rates. Additionally, providing nutritious meals can improve children's overall well-being by increasing their energy levels and concentration in class. As a result, students may become more engaged and participate in classroom activities. The parents believed that the school-based feeding program has led to increased attendance and participation of their child in class discussions. According to the participants, because of the meals, the children are motivated to attend school. One participant (PR9) mentioned that the meals make it easier for their child to go to school because it gives them the energy to focus and participate, leading to better attendance and involvement in activities. This is similar to the study of Carreon et al. (2021) who emphasized the role of adequate nutrition in reducing absenteeism due to health-related issues

ing program. Lu and Dacal (2020) also arrived at the same conclusion, emphasizing that after the program began, the student beneficiaries of SBFP got better grades and performed well in academics. Additionally, this finding is further reinforced by Carreon et al. (2021) whose study observed that students' average grades across subjects improved after participating in the program. This improvement suggests that better nutritional intake and improved health directly correlate with enhanced cognitive abilities and academic achievement.

among students. Furthermore, this outcome aligns with the findings of Solania and Cubilla's (2020) study which highlighted that SBFP not only addresses nutritional needs but also encourages regular school attendance. Their study showed that monthly attendance records during the program period showed consistently high attendance rates ranging from 92 to 100 across participating schools. Through observations and the feedback, they received from their children regarding the influence of the school-based feeding program, the participants validated their claims that the meals provided by the program greatly improved the school attendance and participation of their children. According to one participant (PS5), their child mentioned how meals at school provide energy for active participation in class and help with regular attendance. The same results were found in Comighud's (2019) study revealing a significant improvement in students' academic performance and participation which is evident in their increased enthusiasm to attend courses on a regular and punctual basis, improved grades, and increased participation in various school activities. This research results back up the notion that providing food at school during the school day has a direct positive influence on learner attendance. Since good nutrition makes them healthier, this

Fig. 4. Parents’ Perception of The Results of School-Based Feeding Programs on Their Children’s Education

lessens the chance of them missing school due to sickness. In a parallel study, the same conclusion was made by Maijo (2018), supporting this study’s finding that school feeding has a positive impact not only on school attendance but also on an enhanced school climate, higher enrollment, and better learning results, ultimately lowering the dropout rate. This is also supported by the study by Sahagun (2022), who stated that the nutritional support of the school feeding

program contributed to increased school attendance and improved daily student performance, potentially reducing mental and behavioral issues associated with inadequate nutrition. Figure 4 shows parents’ perception of the results of school-based Feeding programs on Their Children’s Education and the two emergence of the themes of better academic performance, improved nutritional status, and increased school attendance and participation.

3.3. Educational Management Insights Drawn from the Findings of the Study Focused on School-Based Feeding Programs—Obtaining insight from parents on the impact of the school-based feeding program on their child’s nutrition and education is critical because parents have valuable firsthand knowledge and observations about their child’s dietary habits, nutritional needs, and academic performance. By gath-

ering their insights, educators, and policymakers can gain a thorough understanding of how families perceive and experience the feeding program, allowing for more informed decision-making and program improvements. Involving parents in the evaluation process promotes a sense of ownership and collaboration in the program. When parents feel valued and included in discussions about their children’s well-being

and education, they are more likely to actively participate and support the school's initiatives. Their insights can provide useful feedback on the program's effectiveness, as well as suggestions for improvements or expansion. Furthermore, engaging parents in discussions about the school-based feeding program promotes transparency and trust between schools and families. Schools can foster rapport and collaboration with parents by openly communicating the pro-

3.3.1. Importance of Good Nutrition—The implementation of school-based feeding programs emphasizes the importance of good nutrition for children. These programs prioritize providing balanced meals during school hours, addressing students' nutritional needs, particularly those experiencing food insecurity. Additionally, they encourage healthy eating habits and educate children on the benefits of nutrition, allowing them to make informed decisions. Furthermore, school-based feeding programs recognize the relationship between nutrition and academic performance, ensuring that students have the nutrients they need to succeed in the classroom. These programs level the playing field in education by promoting equity and inclusivity, allowing every child to thrive academically and socially. Because of the benefits and advantages that the program offered particularly in improving the children's nutrition and education, the participants learned a valuable lesson regarding the importance of good nutrition. To support children in their education, parents must provide them with proper meals so that they can gain the nutrients and energy needed to participate and focus on the lessons. According to one of the participants (PS1), the health of the children is really important which is why it is also important that they be given enough nutritious food while going to school so that they can learn better. According to Keeley et al. (2019), quality nutrition can disrupt the harmful cycles across

gram's goals, strategies, and outcomes, resulting in a supportive environment conducive to student success. In this section of the study, the discussion will focus on the insights gained by participants regarding the impact of the school-based feeding program on their children's nutrition and education. Through interviews with participants, two main themes emerged, each of which will be comprehensively discussed.

generations where malnutrition leads to poverty and perpetuates malnutrition. Well-nourished children have a solid foundation to reach their fullest potential. This insight is similar to that of Solania and Cubillas (2020), who stated that after the program, the study participants demonstrated very satisfactory knowledge and practices regarding their nutrition. Half of the participants recommended that the policymakers and educational leaders need to give more emphasis on the importance of good nutrition among students especially when they are studying. One of the participants (PS1) mentioned that emphasizing the nutrition of children is paramount to ensuring their overall well-being, particularly as they engage in their studies. She also added that a healthy body nurtured through proper nutrition is essential for academic success and overall development. This study corroborates the results of the study conducted by Mukhamedzhanov et al. (2023) who asserted that the energy and nutrient requirements of school-age children differ significantly from those of adults and are subject to variation. These children derive their energy from food, utilizing it for growth, development, and metabolic functions such as those involving the respiratory, digestive, and circulatory systems, as well as for physical activity. These nutrients must be provided to children to support them in their growth. The importance of good nutrition is also supported by Scaglioni et al. (2018) who underscored the

complex nature of the factors that may influence the dietary habits of children. The authors also advocated for comprehensive educational programs and a supportive family environment to promote healthy eating habits among chil-

dren. The well-being of children relies on the people around them; it is the duty of the parents and the community to give them the necessities they need to develop and grow properly and become dependable adults.

3.3.2. Resource Allocation and Program Implementation—The implementation of school-based feeding programs emphasizes the critical role of good nutrition in children's health and academic success. These initiatives prioritize providing nutritious meals during school hours, particularly for students from economically disadvantaged families who face food insecurity. They also serve as educational platforms for encouraging healthy eating habits and raising nutritional awareness among children, laying the groundwork for lifelong health. Furthermore, these programs help students perform better in school by providing them with the nutrients they need to maintain cognitive function and concentration. More funds should be allocated to the school-based feeding program because it is critical in combating food insecurity and malnutrition among children, particularly those from low-income families. By providing nutritious meals during school hours, the program ensures that children have access to the nutrients they need for growth, development, and overall health. Furthermore, investing in a school-based feeding program can provide long-term benefits to both individuals and society. Proper nutrition is strongly associated with improved academic performance, cognitive function, and overall health. Children who are well-nourished are more likely to succeed academically, which leads to better job opportunities and increased productivity in the future. Furthermore, addressing malnutrition early in life can help prevent chronic diseases and lower healthcare costs in the long term. Most of the participants are grateful to the program because it provided their children with

proper meals that they sometimes cannot afford due to poverty. Some of them hope that this program will last so that it can help more people while others said that they wish the government would allocate more funds to this program to expand its coverage. According to one of the participants (PR10), programs like this are very helpful to children because they need this support the most and she also added that she hoped that schools would be given enough budget for that. This is similar to the assertions made by Drake (2020) saying that expanding the coverage of school feeding programs and enhancing the quality of existing initiatives are imperative steps to maximize their benefits for children and adolescents. Drake also added that school feeding programs have been and will remain crucial for providing essential nutrients, enhancing academic performance, and fostering a healthy lifestyle, particularly in low and middle-income countries. Consequently, there is a robust political determination to continue funding new programs and expanding existing ones. Proper funding is necessary for the success of a certain program especially if the goal of the said program benefits a large quantity of people. In the context of this study, the children benefit the most from the school-based feeding program because they are the sole beneficiaries. Based on the participants' responses, they recommend that policymakers and educational leaders allocate enough of the budget for properly implementing the feeding program in respective schools. This discovery aligns with the report authored by Cervantes (2024), which states that, as per the chairperson of the House Committee on Basic Education and Cul-

Fig. 5. Educational Management Insights Drawn from The Findings of The Study Focused on School-Based Feeding Program

ture, the Department of Education’s (DepEd) school-based feeding program requires a comprehensive whole-of-government strategy to address the challenge of undernutrition among school children adequately. Additionally, the

report of Aurelio (2023) stipulates that this year, the proposed funding for feeding the children is almost sixteen billion pesos (approximately P15.795 billion) which could provide 857 million meals for nutritionally deficient children.

4. Implications and Future Directions

This chapter offers a concise summary of the research conducted, followed by an analysis of the implications stemming from the findings obtained. Additionally, the study explores potential avenues for further investigation into the long-term benefits of the school-based feeding program aimed at enhancing children’s growth and development and their educational performance.

4.1. Findings—This study explored parents’ perspectives on School-Based Feeding Programs (SBFPs) and their perceptions of the program’s outcomes, guided by Maslow’s Hierarchy of Needs (1943) and Aaron Beck’s Cognitive Behavioral Theory. Maslow’s theory suggests that individuals’ physiological needs, in-

cluding nutrition, must be met before higher-order needs, such as academic achievement, can be fulfilled. This study recognizes SBFPs as crucial interventions that satisfy children’s physiological needs, enabling them to focus better on learning and academic success. Moreover, Aaron Beck’s Cognitive Behavioral The-

ory posits that individuals' thoughts, emotions, and behaviors are interconnected and can influence their overall well-being. In the context of SBFPs, parents' perceptions of the program's outcomes reflect their beliefs about how nutritional support impacts their children's cognitive functioning and educational outcomes. By exploring these perceptions through narrative inquiry, this study aims to uncover how parents' beliefs and interpretations align with or diverge from cognitive behavioral principles, particularly regarding the cognitive benefits attributed to improved nutrition through SBFPs. Three overarching themes emerged from the narratives of participating parents regarding their attitudes and experiences with SBFPs. These themes reflect not only the practical implications of the program in terms of nutrition provision but also the psychological and emotional impacts perceived by parents. Additionally, two distinct themes emerged concerning how parents perceive the tangible outcomes of SBFPs on their children's academic achievements, which were crucial for understanding the program's effectiveness through the lens of cognitive behavioral theory. Furthermore, participants' insights revealed two prominent themes regarding the perceived influence of SBFPs on their children's nutritional health and educational experiences. These themes highlight the multifaceted impacts of SBFPs beyond mere nutritional supplementation, shedding light on broader implications for academic outcomes and children's overall development. By integrating Maslow's Hierar-

4.2. Implications—The research findings underscore the significant impact of school-based feeding programs on children's physical health, which contributes to their overall well-being and academic achievement. These programs ensure access to essential nutrients for growth and development by providing nutritious meals in schools. Recognizing the importance

of Needs and Cognitive Behavioral Theory into the interpretation of parents' narratives, this study provides insights into the effectiveness of SBFPs but also contributes theoretically to understanding how these programs address fundamental needs and psychological constructs that underpin children's educational success and well-being. The parents' viewpoints regarding the school-based feeding program encompass improved nutritional status, physical health, and social and emotional well-being. These themes imply that the program significantly contributed to the overall improvement of their children's growth and development. The study highlights the crucial role of school feeding programs in enhancing children's nutritional status. By providing nutritious meals during the school day, these programs address malnutrition and its health and cognitive effects. Schools and policymakers must prioritize implementing and expanding such programs as integral components of promoting child health and well-being. Educators can leverage the positive impact of better nutrition on students' physical and cognitive development to enhance learning outcomes. Integrating nutrition education into curricula empowers students to make informed dietary choices. Efforts should focus on ensuring the sustainability and accessibility of school-based feeding programs, especially in marginalized communities and food-insecure regions. Stakeholders support children's overall development and academic success by investing in these initiatives and promoting nutritional awareness.

of such programs, educators and policymakers should integrate them into school settings to meet immediate nutritional needs and promote long-term health outcomes. Improved physical health among students creates conducive learning environments, fostering alertness, focus, and academic participation. Prioritizing the sustainability and scalability of these programs was es-

sential for equitable access, particularly for students from low-income families. By investing in children's physical health through these initiatives, stakeholders lay the groundwork for better educational outcomes and holistic development, nurturing healthy, active, and thriving individuals. The study's findings underscore the diverse benefits of school-based feeding programs, extending beyond nutritional provision to enhance children's social and emotional well-being. By offering meals during school hours, these programs alleviate food insecurity among students, fostering a sense of belonging and community inclusion. Educational institutions should recognize the importance of nurturing supportive environments where children feel valued, contributing to their socioemotional development and academic success. Incorporating communal dining experiences into the school day ensures access to nutritious meals and promotes social interaction and peer relationships, fostering a sense of community among students. Furthermore, educators could leverage the positive social dynamics facilitated by these programs to implement social-emotional learning initiatives, teaching essential skills like empathy, cooperation, and resilience. Stakeholders facilitate holistic development by addressing food insecurity and promoting social connectedness within the school community, paving the way for positive educational experiences and long-term well-being. The themes clearly indicate that parents perceive the school-based feeding program as highly advantageous in improving their children's nutrition, growth, and development. To delve deeper into the topic, attention is shifted to the program's impact on the child's educational experience. Two themes emerged from the parents' perspectives, highlighting better academic performance and increased school attendance and participation. The study underscores the importance of school-based feeding programs in enhancing academic performance by addressing children's nutritional needs. Access to nu-

tritious meals during the school day provides students with the energy and focus required for effective participation in classroom activities. Incorporating these programs into school settings was crucial for promoting student success, as they create environments conducive to active learning and cognitive skill mastery. Educators can leverage the positive impact of nutrition on academic performance to implement interventions that address learning barriers and promote equitable outcomes. Ensuring the sustainability and accessibility of these programs, particularly for marginalized communities and food-insecure students, closes achievement gaps and fosters academic excellence. By investing in children's nutritional well-being through these initiatives, stakeholders improve the educational experience and set the stage for lifelong learning and success. The study also highlights the significant impact of school-based feeding programs on attendance and participation, emphasizing the importance of addressing fundamental needs for educational engagement. These programs incentivize regular attendance by providing nutritious meals, reducing absenteeism, and improving overall attendance rates. Academic institutions and policymakers should recognize their role in alleviating hunger and facilitating access to education, fostering a positive learning environment. Improved attendance offers students more opportunities for engagement, interaction, and participation in learning activities. Educators can leverage this connection to develop strategies promoting student attendance and learning involvement. Efforts should ensure the accessibility and sustainability of these programs, particularly for vulnerable populations, to maximize their impact on academic outcomes. Prioritizing nutrition support in educational settings fosters inclusive environments where all students can thrive academically and socially. Insights were gleaned from participants' perspectives on the impact of the school-based feeding program on their

children's nutritional health, growth, development, and academic experience. These insights were categorized into two themes: emphasizing the importance of good nutrition among children and the need for proper resource allocation and program implementation to expand the program further. The study's findings stress the importance of good nutrition for schoolchildren's overall well-being and academic success. Access to nutritious meals was vital for students to maintain the energy, focus, and cognitive function needed for a successful school day. Educational institutions and policymakers should prioritize initiatives promoting healthy eating habits and equitable access to nutritious foods. Educators can help students make informed dietary choices and develop lifelong healthy habits by integrating nutrition education into the curriculum. Schools should collaborate with community partners to develop comprehensive wellness programs addressing students' nutritional needs. Recognizing the connection between nutrition and learning, educators can advocate for policies prioritizing

student well-being and fostering positive learning environments. Promoting good nutrition among schoolchildren lays the foundation for improved educational outcomes and nurtures a generation of healthy, resilient individuals. The investigation underscores the urgent need for sufficient funding to effectively implement and expand school-based feeding programs. This financial support was vital for providing nutritious meals to vulnerable children and addressing food insecurity in educational settings. Educational institutions, policymakers, and government agencies must prioritize food supplies, kitchen equipment, staff training, and program administration funding. Additionally, increased funding was necessary to reach more needy children and ensure equitable access to nutrition assistance. Collaboration with external partners can supplement funding sources and enhance program effectiveness. Advocating for robust funding mechanisms and policies was essential for promoting educational equity and student achievement by prioritizing children's nutritional needs.

4.3. Future Directions—This study offers a comprehensive exploration of the parents' viewpoints regarding the school-based feeding program and how they perceive its impact on their children's education. By investigating the viewpoints of the parents, particularly on how they perceive the impact of the school-based feeding program on their children's nutrition and education, valuable data was collected to inform recommendations, suggestions, and future directions for key stakeholders in education, such as policymakers, administrators, teachers, and future researchers. The findings of this study serve as a foundation for evidence-based decision-making and provide practical guidance for adequately implementing the school-based feeding program to address the nutritional needs of children from low-income families. Policy-

makers and policymakers may focus on ensuring school-based feeding programs' long-term viability and effectiveness. This includes investigating long-term funding options and collaborating with various stakeholders. Integrating these programs with other health and education initiatives could increase their impact, but rigorous evaluation was required to identify successful interventions and scale them to reach more children. School Administrators and school administrators can concentrate on improving program implementation and monitoring while ensuring equitable access and meal quality. Engaging local communities and fostering partnerships could increase support for these programs and promote sustainability. Furthermore, incorporating nutrition education into the curriculum supports the goals of feeding pro-

grams by instilling healthy habits in students. For Teachers. Teachers play an essential role in providing nutrition education and promoting student well-being. Training teachers to incorporate healthy eating topics into lesson plans and recognize signs of malnutrition could improve student health and academic performance. Collaboration with school administrators and nutrition experts helps to align academic objectives with feeding program goals. For Researchers, longitudinal studies could help better understand the long-term effects of feeding programs on children's health and academic performance. Evaluating the efficacy of various interventions in diverse settings aids in the identification of cost-effective approaches. Interdisciplinary research encourages holistic interventions that address multiple determinants of child well-being, promoting comprehensive solutions to improve children's lives.

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